

A novel amperometric biosensor for detection of penicillin in milk

Priyabrata Sarkar

Department of Polymer Science and Technology, University of Calcutta, 92, A. P. C. Road, Calcutta-700 009, India

Manuscript received 3 November 1998, revised 3 May 1999, accepted 26 June 1999

A novel disposable screen-printed biosensor for low level detection of penicillin in milk is reported. Penicillin binding protein (PBP) is used for immobilisation of both penicillin and the enzyme conjugate, i.e. β -lactum analogue labelled with the enzyme glucose oxidase (7ACA-GOD) on the working electrode of a screen-printed sensor. The residual glucose oxidase on the electrode is used to catalyse glucose to produce hydrogen peroxide. The amount of GOD immobilised on the surface of the PBP electrode and hence the current is inversely proportional to the penicillin concentration.

Penicillin concentration in milk is an important parameter and this should be checked before consumption. It is necessary to keep the concentration below 5 ppb to avoid any harmful effects on health¹. There are a number of publications on the detection of penicillin in milk. Most of the studies for detection of penicillin employed immobilisation of enzyme penicillinase, which acted as the biocatalyst²⁻⁴. This method is however suitable for detection of high concentration of penicillin (0.1 to 30 mM). The following reaction takes place at the surface of the electrode in presence of penicillinase,

There are conventional laboratory techniques for sensitive test (ppb range) of penicillin. A conductimetric method⁵ used for penicillin G is based on change of conductance due to inhibition by the antibiotic on the growth of *Bacillus stearothermophilus*. High voltage electrophoresis⁶ in 1% agarose gel was used to detect residual antibiotics in milk.

All these methods require laboratory measurements with precision instruments. The procedure in most of the cases is lengthy and costly. None of the above methods could be used for on-site measurement. Amperometric biosensors are known for detection of various species and generally consist of a biocatalyst with electrochemical sensors. The biocatalyst (e.g. enzyme) recognises the substrate to be determined and specifically converts into a product that is detected amperometrically by the adjacent sensor. This allows a sensitive and selective determination of substrates especially biological substrates in presence of complex mixtures. The present study used *screen-printed* disposable electrodes with a novel technique to detect penicillin amperometrically.

Results and Discussion

The critical part of this study was to find a suitable dilution match between penicillin binding protein (PBP) and

the conjugate. Thus various dilutions of PBP and conjugate stock solutions were tried to achieve best results for a low-level detection of penicillin. PBP of 1 : 10, 1 : 50 and 1 : 100 dilution and conjugate of 1 : 50, 1 : 100, 1 : 500, 1 : 1000, 1 : 2000 and 1 : 4000 dilution of the stock solutions were tried. For a given area of the electrode, the combination of the PBP and the conjugate loading should have an optimum value for detection of penicillin in the range of

Fig. 1 Current response from PBP electrode with various loading of PBP and conjugate (corrected for baseline response), potential applied +350 mV vs Ag/AgCl, error bars = SD, $n = 3$

5 to 20 ppb. Fig. 1 depicts the results and a combination of dilutions of 1 : 100 for PBP and 1 : 1000 for conjugate was found optimum since the PBP loading was just sufficient for the conjugate. In all the above experiments the responses were corrected for the baseline response given by the same PBP loading without the conjugated enzyme. Also average of three reading for the same sample was plotted. Fig. 2 shows a typical response obtained by the penicillin sensor for 0, 5, 10 and 20 ppb in milk. A comparison of the results obtained from the two methods is presented in Fig. 3. The

Fig. 2 Typical response curve of a penicillin sensor for various concentrations of penicillin in milk; potential applied +350 mV vs Ag/AgCl.

Fig. 3. Calibration curves of penicillin in milk using (a) competitive and (b) sequential assay with a penicillin sensor; potential applied +350 mV vs Ag/AgCl; error bars = SD, $n = 3$.

sequential assay gave a linearity in the range of our experiments whereas competitive assay gave poorer trend line with large error bars.

The disposable screen-printed penicillin sensor unlike other conventional enzyme electrodes is capable of detecting very low concentration of penicillin (5–20 ppb), limit of detection being 2.5 ppb, making its use essential for measuring penicillin in milk. The coefficient of variance remained below 10% for all the measurements. Unlike other conventional detection methods, these electrodes are simple to use and the production/operation involves low cost. Though both *sequential* and *competitive* modes gave fairly good results, the former is more accurate and consistent.

Experimental

The penicillin binding protein (PBP) and 7ACA-GOD

were both obtained from Cranfield Biotechnology Centre, UK. The phosphate buffer (Sigma) and HEC (Fluka) were used. The substrate for the sensors was 250 μm thick polyester sheet (Cadillac Plastic Ltd., Swindon, UK). The basal tracks and bases of the three electrodes were printed using MCA 45R carbon ink (MCA Services Ltd., Melbourn, Cambs., UK). The electrocatalytic material (aqueous based) for the circular WE was made from 1 part MCA 4A rhodinated carbon powder and 4 parts of 2% (w/v) HEC in phosphate buffer⁷. The material for the reference electrode was 15% silver chloride in silver paste (MCA). To protect the underlying basal tracks from solution, an epoxy based protective coating ink 242-SB (Agmet ESL Ltd., Reading, UK) was deposited. A DEK 248 screen printer (DEK Printing Machines, Weymouth, UK) was used to print the electrodes.

PBP stock solution (6 mg/ml) was diluted in 0.05 M carbonate buffer (pH 9.6) to the required value. A 4 μl of this solution was pipetted onto the WE and dried at room temperature for 1 h on an orbital shaker (100 rpm). These electrodes were then baked in the oven at 120° for 10 min and stored at 4° under dry conditions until required.

Two different protocols were followed to detect penicillin: (i) a *competitive* assay where both analyte and the conjugate competed for the PBP binding sites, and (ii) a *sequential assay* where penicillin would first bind to the PBP binding sites and the conjugate would then bind to the rest of the active sites available on the surface of the electrode. In both the procedures penicillin concentration in analyte was inversely proportional to the current response. The interaction between the immobilised conjugated enzyme, GOD and the substrate, glucose (contained in the buffer) resulted in the formation of electrochemically active product, hydrogen peroxide, the quantity of which could be related to the amount of free analyte present. The following reactions occurred at the electrode surface:

Hydrogen peroxide was then oxidised on the working electrode when poised at appropriate potential, through the following reaction:

The current was proportional to the concentration of hydrogen peroxide which in turn was dependent on the amount of conjugate immobilised.

A serial dilution of a freshly prepared penicillin stock solution was made in penicillin-free whole milk (from supermarket) containing 0.1% Tween 20 yielding penicillin

solutions in the required ppb range. The conjugate stock solution (3.3 mg ml^{-1}) was diluted to the desired range in 0.1 M phosphate buffer containing 0.1% Tween 20.

Competition assay : PBP electrodes were treated with a mixture of equal volumes of the analyte and conjugate solutions ($10 \mu\text{l}$ aliquots) for 4 min at 64° in a sealed humid incubation chamber. The electrodes were washed (10 forward/backward motion) in series with (a) 0.1 M phosphate buffer + 0.1% Tween 20, (b) 0.1 M phosphate buffer, (c) reverse osmosis water.

Sequential assay : A $10 \mu\text{l}$ of analyte was pipetted on the PBP electrode and incubated for 10 min at 64° . The electrodes were then washed and dried. These electrodes were treated with conjugate solution for 4 min at 64° and subsequently washed as above.

The electrodes were placed in 0.5 M glucose in 0.1 M phosphate buffer, containing 0.1 M KCl electrolyte and the WE poised at a potential of $+350 \text{ mV}$ versus Ag/AgCl reference electrode. The working potential of $+350 \text{ mV}$ vs Ag/AgCl was chosen to minimise the electrochemical interfer-

ence due to oxidation of easily oxidisable compounds, which might be present in the analyte. The amperometric response of the device was recorded after 2 min.

Acknowledgement

The author wishes to acknowledge Indian National Science Academy and Royal Society (London) for awarding fellowship at Cranfield University, UK.

References

- 1 O N Okigbo and G H Richardson, *J Food Protection*, 1985, **48**, 979
- 2 Eppelsheim, R Aubeck and N Hampp, *J Membrane Sci*, 1995, **100**, 131
- 3 E Leszczynska, R Koncki and S Glab, *Chem Anal*, 1996, **41**, 839
- 4 M Thust, M J Schoning, J Vetter, P Kordos and H Luth, *Anal Chim Acta*, 1996, **323**, 115
- 5 H C Chen and T C Chang, *J Dairy Sci*, 1994, **77**, 1515
- 6 P Krcmar and V Ruzickova, *Vet Med -Czech*, 1996, **41**, 93
- 7 P Sarkar and A P F Turner, *Fresenius J Anal Chem*, 1999, in press